

USING INTERNET RESOURCES IN AN ENGLISH LESSON**Ishanova Gauxar Djambulovna¹**

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Due to the rapid increase in the volume of information, knowledge in itself ceases to be an end in itself, they become a condition for the successful realization of the individual in her future professional activities, in this regard, at present, Internet resources are widely used in teaching a foreign language. The process of teaching a foreign language is multifaceted, the main goal of which is the development of a communicative personality that will be able to participate in intercultural communication. The main difficulty in mastering a foreign language is the development of skills and abilities of listening and speaking. Internet resources are of invaluable help in this regard.

Key words

Internet, communicative, e-mail, electronic, speech, teaching, error, skills, writing abilities.

Communication in virtual reality is carried out using e-mail, which can be used to master intercultural competence in the following ways:

Establishing friendly correspondence.

International exchange of letters can be carried out in any class and at any level of language proficiency. In addition to the purposeful use of the language being studied, the establishment of friendly contacts, and therefore the study of culture, electronic correspondence has its advantages over paper correspondence: it is faster, more convenient and cheaper. To obtain optimal results from this type of activity, it is necessary to dwell on some difficulties that may arise in the course of work.

Teachers who have integrated e-mail into the educational process make note the lack of depth in the content of the correspondence. Initial interest fades quickly and learners find themselves in a quandary of not knowing what to write about. In order that teacher should avoid disappointment, it is necessary to correlate this type of work with the general curriculum and it must not be left to chance. For instance, you can invite students to ask their pen pals about a particular topic and, based on the results, make a report to the class. Not all letters receive answers, which entails the deepest disappointment. To prevent this from

happening, you can invite learners to communicate with several partners at once (in the same group or in a parallel one, in another city or even country).

Preference is given to work in small groups, without strict control from the teacher. The best results are achieved by allowing learners to choose a topic for discussion themselves, and not unquestioningly follow the instructions of the teacher and the majority of the group (in this case, a new group is simply formed).

This form of conducting a lesson will increase students' interest in learning English, consolidate their understanding of the fact that it is necessary to speak a foreign language in the modern world, give students a lot of new information about the culture and traditions of other countries, and introduce them to the existing education systems in them.

The pedagogical conditions for the development of students' skills to select the necessary information of a regional orientation are: the establishment of integrative links between traditional and non-traditional forms of education using textbooks, excerpts from feature films, and authentic materials from Internet resources, the disclosure of pedagogical opportunities. The Internet in the process of learning a foreign language; building an algorithm for searching for the necessary information; actualization of the subjective regional experience of students; designing independent and creative forms of education; involvement of students in active professional search activities: preparation of term papers of a professional orientation.

To be effective, the use of e-mail must be purposeful. The set of tasks can be as follows:

- ✚ place an ad about finding friends on different sites by correspondence;
- ✚ write information about yourself;
- ✚ send several messages, for example, 2-3 per week;
- ✚ in order to get an answer, ask your questions at the end of the message;
- ✚ accept at least three replies to your messages;
- ✚ Provide a full report on the work done: what you did, what came out of it, what you learned new, how you evaluate the task.

The key feature of this virtual educational space is the creation of three areas in which teams participating in the project can take part: a project to cut environmental problems on a global scale, a project of modern urbanism and a cybernetic project. Internet resources increase the motivation of students to develop self-educational skills aimed at acquiring, analyzing and adapting new experience and knowledge.

As part of the use of Internet resources in English lessons, students learn to work with text in a research format, work with digital and graphic information, analyze it and, based on it, create their own ideas, projects, messages.

Thus, using the information resources of the Internet, it is likely, integrating them into the educational process, to more effectively solve a number of didactic tasks in the lesson:

- ✚ to form reading skills and abilities, directly using the materials of the network of varying degrees of complexity;
- ✚ improve listening skills based on authentic Internet audio texts, also prepared by the teacher accordingly;
- ✚ to improve the skills of monologue and dialogic utterance on the basis of a problematic discussion of the materials presented by the teacher or one of the students of the network;
- ✚ improve writing skills, individually or in writing compiling answers to partners, participating in the preparation of abstracts, essays, other epistolary products of joint activities of partners;
- ✚ replenish your vocabulary, both active and passive, with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language, reflecting a certain stage in the development of the culture of the people, the social and political structure of society;
- ✚ get acquainted with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, features of the speech behavior of various peoples in the conditions of communication, features of the culture, traditions of the country of the language being studied;
- ✚ to form a sustainable motivation for foreign language activity of students in the classroom based on the systematic use of "live" materials, discussion of not only questions for textbook texts, but also "hot" problems that are of interest to everyone.

The Internet is accessible and rich in resources, but these advantages are also a source of problems: the almost unlimited volume of unstructured information makes it difficult to find the necessary material, and the lack of control over the quality and content of documents placed in the virtual space leads to the appearance (along with high-quality materials prepared by professionals) base information products.

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